

ANIMAL SPECIES AND BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE OF WEST DIVISION OF CHHINDWARA DISTRICT OF MADHYA PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out in the West region of Chhindwara district of Madhya Pradesh (India) to document the diversity and utility of fauna. Many of the wild life species are gradually vanishing from our forest. The biological imbalance created due to disappearance of particular species which have put may problem. The national forest policy 1952 has laid special emphasis on preservation of wild animals. The inhabitants of the region are dependent up to a large extent on wild resources for their remedial needs. The region is rich in faunal diversity having **183** species belonging to **146** genera and **94** families. Out of the documented animal species **36** were mammals and **125** birds **14** reptiles and **8** fishes in this area. This study will be helpful in developing a comprehensive data base on the faunal resources to strengthen the care system in the area and in conserving the faunal resources for the

prosperity of the region.

KEYWORDS: Biodiversity, Faunal resource, Care system, Disappearance, Conservation.

INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity is very important for ecosystem. Biotic and abiotic factors are interconnected with each other. Biodiversity is term that describes the total variability among organisms and the habitats in which they live. Species are the fundamental units of biodiversity and they have either direct or indirect links with each other in a given habitat. We are bound to loose

species or have them drastically changed from a specified habitat if their component species become extinct. Presently, the rate of extinction of species is alarming faster. In other words, even we do not know the economic value of many species we are losing at a remarkably faster rate (Patil 2000).

In Chhindwara district the tribal and rural communities use arthropods for medicinal food and cultural purposes their traditional knowledge reflects a strong bond with nature and plays an important role in local healthcare and livelihoods preserving and documenting this Indigenous wisdom is essential for biodiversity conservation sustainable resources use and safeguarding valuable cultural heritage for future generations (Bagde and Jain 2016).

In India, there are many communities residing in diverse geographical and climatic zones. They represent distinct traditions, life-styles and cultures. People living in villages and far-flung areas depend largely on forest resources for maintaining their day-to-day needs like medicine, food, fuel and household articles (Chhetri et al., 2005), as animal and plants have been playing a vital role in the socio-economic development of such regions (Tiwari et al., 2010a).

The tribal communities of Chhindwara rely on traditional knowledge for agriculture, animal husbandry, and resource use, which supports their livelihoods. These practices also preserve cultural identity and promote local environmental awareness. (Bagde and Jain 2017).

STUDY AREA

The West Chhindwara Division is situated between the parallels of latitude 21 Deg. 52' to 22 Deg. 42' north and between meridian of longitude 78 Deg. 14' 43'' and 79 Deg. 01' 52'' East. The Division is bounded on the North by protected forest of Hoshangabad and Narsighpur forest Division, reserve and protected forest of East, forest of South Chhindwara Division on the southern side and protected forest of Betul district on the West. The total area of the Division is 175945.122 hectares. The tract of West Chhindwara Division is plain to undulating and maximum area is hilly and rugged. Main forests of this Division are confined to ranges of Satpura hills and Chhindwara plateau. The western and north western part of the division is mostly hilly whereas eastern and southern part is mostly plain. The shape of the division is like a big cleft which forms a deep a very narrow valley of Kanhan river which flows towards south and meet the plains of Nagpur. The highest place in the division is in

Tamia range; protected forest block at 1211meter altitude and the lowest place is in Jhirpa range, at 387 meter altitude, (Bagde, 2015).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was taken up in the west division of Chhindwara range. The survey work was conducted during the period of July 2024 to December 2025. Observations were recorded on habit, habitat, soil details of association and other peculiarities. Primary and secondary data were collected. Primary data was collected by field study and secondary data was collected by forest office of west division of Chhindwara. Faunal photographs were identified by standard literature, Ali and Preter (1996) and Ali (2000).

OBSERVATIONS

Table-1: Faunal diversity of West Forest Division of Chhindwara.

S.No.	English name	Scientific name	Local name	Family/ Class/Order
1.	Rhesus macaque	<i>Macaca mulatta</i>	Bander	Circopthecidae/ M
2.	Common langur	<i>Presbytis entellus</i>	langur	Colobidae/ M
3.	Longeared hedghog	<i>Hemiechinus auritus collaris</i>	Shahi	Erinacidae/ M
4.	Musk-shrew	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	Chhachhundar	Tupaiaidae/ M
5.	Short nosed fruit bat	<i>Cynopterus sphinx</i>	Chamgadar	Pteropodidae/ M
6.	Flying fox	<i>Pteropus gogantious</i>	Gadal/Badur	Pteropodidae/ M
7.	Indian pangolin	<i>Manis crassicaudata</i>	Shilu/Kholmadar	Manidae/ M
8.	Scaly ant eater	<i>Manis tetradactyla</i>	Bajra kit	Manidae/ M
9.	Jackal	<i>Canis aureus</i>	Siyar/Gidar	Canidae/ M
10.	Indian fox	<i>Vulpes bengalensis</i>	Lomdi	Canidae/M
11.	Wild dog	<i>Canis alpinus</i>	Sonkutta	Canidae/ M
12.	Tiger	<i>Panthera tigris</i>	Bagh	Felidae/ M
13.	Leopard	<i>Panthera pardus</i>	Tendua/Gulbagh	Felidae/M
14.	Jungle cat	<i>Felis chaus</i>	Jangli billi	Felidae/M
15.	Common mongoose	<i>Herpestis edwardssi</i>	Newla	Herpestidae/M
16.	Striped hyaena	<i>Hyaena hyaena</i>	Lakadbagga	Hyaenidae/M
17.	Honey badger	<i>Melivra capensis</i>	Bijju	Mustelidae/M
18.	Sloth bear	<i>Melursus ursinus</i>	Richh	Ursidae/M
19.	Indian porcupine	<i>Hystix indica</i>	Shehi	Hysticidae/M
20.	Indian hare	<i>Lepus nigricollis</i>	Khargosh	Leporidae/M
21.	Field rat	<i>Bandicota bengalensis</i>	Chuha	Muridae/M
22.	Bandicoot	<i>Neosocia bandicota</i>	Chunse	Muridae/M
23.	House rat	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	Chuha	Muridae/M
24.	Indian bush rat	<i>Golund ellioti</i>	Chuha	Muridae/M
25.	Five striped squirrel	<i>Funambulus pennanti</i>	Gilhari	Sciuridae/M
26.	Three striped squirrel	<i>Funambulus palmarum</i>	Gilhari	Sciuridae/M
27.	Indian black antelope	<i>Antilope cervicapra</i>	Krishn mrig	Antilopinae/M
28.	Indian gazelle	<i>Gazell gazell</i>	Chinkara	Antilopinae/M

29.	Blue bull	<i>Boselaphus tragocamelus</i>	Neelgay	Antilopinae/M
30.	Four horned antelope	<i>Tetracerus quadricornis</i>	Chausinga	Antilopinae/M
31.	Indian bison	<i>Bos gaurus</i>	Gour	Bovidae/M
32.	Barking deer	<i>Muntiacus muntjak</i>	Kotri/Bhedki	Cervidae/M
33.	Sambar	<i>Cervus unicolor</i>	Sambhar	Cervidae/M
34.	Spotted deer	<i>Axis axis</i>	Chital	Cervidae/M
35.	Indian wild boar	<i>Sus scrofa cristata</i>	Barha	Suidae/M
36.	Mouse deer	<i>Tragulus meminna</i>	Pisora	Tragulidae/M
37.	White wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	Dhovan	Motacillidae/ B
38.	Indian ring dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocta</i>	Fakta	Collumbidae/ B
39.	Pied hornbill	<i>Anthracoceres coronatus</i>	Ghanchuri	Bucerotidae/B
40.	Large pied wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	Khanjan	Motacillidae/ B
41.	Collard bushchat	<i>Saxicola tarqnata</i>	Kharpida	Turdinae/ B
42.	Blue winged teal	<i>Anus querquedula</i>	Khera	Anatidae/ B
43.	House swift	<i>Apus affinis</i>	Babilo batasi	Apodidae/ B
44.	Stone curlew	<i>Burhinus oedicnemus</i>	Barsiri	Burhinidae/ B
45.	Weaver bird	<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>	Baya	Ploceidae/ B
46.	Alpine swift	<i>Apus melba</i>	Bada batasi	Apodidae/ B
47.	Large egret	<i>Egretta alba</i>	Bada bagla	Ardeidae/ B
48.	Blue checked bee eater	<i>Merops superciliosus</i>	Patringa	Meropidae/ B
49.	Blue tailed bee eater	<i>Merops philipinus</i>	Bada patringa	Meropidae/ B
50.	Redvented bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	Bulbul	Pycnontidae/ B
51.	Small minivet	<i>Pericrocotus cinnamomus</i>	Bulal chasm saheli	Campephagidae/ B
52.	Common quail	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>	Bater	Phasiamidae/ B
53.	Common crane	<i>Grus grus</i>	Saras	Cruidae/ B
54.	Black headed myna	<i>Sturnus pogodarum</i>	Brahman myna	Sturnidae/ B
55.	Chestnut ballied nuthatch	<i>Sitta castanea</i>	Kthphodia	Sittidae/ B
56.	Velvet fronted nuthatch	<i>Sitta frontalis</i>	Kthphodawa	Sittidae/ B
57.	Golden backed woodpecker	<i>Dinopium bengalensis</i>	Kthphoda	Picidae/ B
58.	Yellow froned pied woodpecker	<i>Picoides manrattensis</i>	Kthphoda	Picidae/ B
59.	Heart spotted woodpecker	<i>Hemicircu sconente</i>	Kthphoda	Picidae/ B
60.	Blue rock pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i>	Kabutar	Collumbidae/ B
61.	Black winged kite	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	Kapasi	Accipitridae/ B
62.	Large cuckoo	<i>Coradina novacholladiae</i>	Kasaya	Campephagidae/ B
63.	Kestrel	<i>Falcotinnunculus</i>	Korutiya	Accipitridae/ B
64.	Koel	<i>Eudynamys scolopaceae</i>	Koyal	Cuculidae/ B
65.	Black capped kingfisher	<i>Haleyan Pileata</i>	Korila	Alcedinidae/ B
66.	House crow	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	Kaua	Covidae/ B
67.	Pied bushchat	<i>Saxicola caprata</i>	Kala pidda	Turdinae/ B
68.	Black partridge	<i>Francolinus francolinus</i>	Kala titar	Phasiamidae/ B
69.	Brown partridge	<i>Francolinus pictus</i>	Bhura titar	Phasiamidae/ B
70.	White eyed pochard	<i>Arthya nyrola</i>	Kurachia	Anatidae/ B
71.	Common teal	<i>Anus crecea</i>	Kera	Anatidae/ B
72.	Rufaus backer shrike	<i>Lanius schach</i>	Kagla latora	Lamidae/ B

73.	Moorhen	<i>Pirphyrio porphyrio</i>	Kalim	Rallidae/ B
74.	Indian robin	<i>Saxicolides falcata</i>	Kalchuri	Turdinae/ B
75.	Mahalot	<i>Dendrocitta vagabunda</i>	Mahalat	Covidae/ B
76.	Coucal	<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	Mokha	Cuculidae/ B
77.	Common pea fowl	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	Mor	Phasiamidae/ B
78.	Common myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	Myna	Sturnidae/ B
79.	Pied kingfisher	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	Kilkila	Alcenididae/ B
80.	White breasted kingfisher	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	Kilkila	Alcenididae/ B
81.	Little egret	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	Kilchia	Ardeidae/ B
82.	Pheasant tailed jacana	<i>Hydrophasianus chirurgus</i>	Pihua	Jacanidae/ B
83.	Yellow wagtail	<i>Motacilla glava</i>	Pilakh	Motacillidae/B
84.	Grey wagtail	<i>Motacilla capica</i>		Motacillidae/B
85.	Pied crested cuckoo	<i>Clamator jacobinus</i>	Papiha/Chatak	Cuculidae/ B
86.	Gray headed myna	<i>Stururus malabaricus</i>	Pavai	Sturnidae/ B
87.	Green bee eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	Patringa	Meropidae/B
88.	Crested bunbing	<i>Melophus lathami</i>	Pathar chitra	Emberizidae/B
89.	Little cormorant	<i>Phalacrocora xnizer</i>	Pankaua	<i>Phalacrocoracidae/B</i>
90.	Shoveller	<i>Anus clypeata</i>	Panao tilari	Anatidae/ B
91.	Large Indian parakeet	<i>Psittacula eupatria</i>	Ram tota	Psittacidae/B
92.	Grey lit	<i>Parus major</i>	Ram gangara	Paridae/B
93.	Yellow checked lit	<i>Parus xanthogenys</i>	Ram gangara	Paridae/B
94.	King vulture	<i>Torgas calvus</i>	Rajgighha	Accipitridae/ B
95.	Purple sun bird	<i>Nectarinia asiatica</i>	Shakar khora	Nectarinidae/ B
96.	Tickell's blue flycatcher	<i>Muscicapatickel ling</i>	Shama	Muscicapinae/B
97.	Shama	<i>Copsychus malabaricus</i>	Shama	Muscicapinae/B
98.	Blue headed rock thrust	<i>Monticola cinclorhynchus</i>	Shama	Muscicapidae/B
99.	White throated ground thrust	<i>Zoothera citrina</i>	Shama	Muscicapidae/B
	Crested hawk eagle	<i>Spizaetus cirrhatus</i>	Shahbaj	Accipitridae/ B
100.	Iora	<i>Aegithina tiphia</i>	Shanbiji	Irenidae/B
101.	Lesser whistling teal	<i>Dendrocygna javanica</i>	Silhi	Anatidae/ B
102.	Sarus crane	<i>Grus antigone</i>	Sarus	Cruidae/B
103.	Slaty headed scimitar bulbular	<i>Pomatorhinus schisticeps</i>	Sat bahan	Muscicapidae/B
104.	Jungal babblar	<i>Turdoides striatus</i>	Sat bhai	Muscicapidae/B
105.	Quaker babblar	<i>Alcippe poioicephale</i>	Sat bhai	Muscicapidae/B
106.	Brahmini duck	<i>Tadorna ferruginea</i>	Surkhab	Anatidae/ B
107.	Red shank	<i>Tringa totanus</i>	Surma	Charadriidae/B
108.	White ibis	<i>Threskiornis</i>	Safed buja	<i>Threskiornithidae/B</i>
109.	White scavenger vulture	<i>Neophron perencoprerus</i>	Safed giddh	Accipitridae/ B
110.	Grey partridge	<i>Francolinus pondicerianus</i>	Safed titar	Phasiamidae/ B
111.	Paradise flycatcher	<i>Terpsiphone paradisi</i>	Sun bulbul dudhraj	Muscicapinae/B
112.	Black napped blue flycatcher	<i>Monarcha azurea azurea</i>	Sun bulbul dudhraj	Muscicapinae/B
113.	Crested serpent eagle	<i>Spilornis cheela</i>	Dograbil	Accipitridae/ B
114.	Owl	<i>Bubo bubo</i>	Ullu	Stricidae/B

115.	Painted stork	<i>Ibis leucocephalus</i>	Janghil/Dokh	Ciconidas/B
116.	Red spur fowl	<i>Galloperdix spondica</i>	Jangli murgi	Phasiamidae/ B
117.	Crimsonbreasted barbot coppersmith	<i>Negalaima haemacephla</i>	Chhota basantha	Capitonidae/B
118.	Estern golden plover	<i>Pluvialis dominica</i>	Chhota batan	Charadridae/B
119.	Comman king fisher	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	Chhota kilkila	Alcedinidae/B
120.	Tufted duck	<i>Anthya fukugula</i>	Dubaru	Anatidae/ B
121.	Magpie robin	<i>Copsychus saularis</i>	Daiya	Muscicapidae/B
122.	White spotted flycatcher	<i>Rhipidura albicolis</i>	Chakdil	Muscicapinae/B
123.	White browed fentail flycatcher	<i>Rhipidura aureola</i>	Chakdil	Muscicapinae/B
124.	Fontail snipe	<i>Capelle gelliango</i>	Chaha	Charadridae/B
125.	Common pariah kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	Cheel	Accipitridae/ B
126.	Common hornbill	<i>Tocus birostris</i>	Chalotra	Bucerotidae/B
127.	Ashy wren warbler	<i>Prinia socialis</i>	Futki	Muscicapidae/B
128.	Tickellus flower peaker	<i>Dicaeum erythrarhynchus</i>	Fulchuki	Dicaeidae/B
129.	Fire breasted flower peaker	<i>Dicaeum ignipectus</i>	Fulchuki	Dicaeidae/B
130.	Rose ringed parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	Tota	Psittacidae/B
131.	Indian whiskered tern	<i>Chilonias hybrida</i>	Tehri kurri	Laridae/B
132.	Ashy shallow shrike	<i>Artamus fusus</i>	Tagaria babil	Diccuidae/B
133.	Red Jungle fowl	<i>Gallus gallus</i>	Jangli murgi	Phasiamidae/B
134.	Jangle crow	<i>Corvus macrorhynchus</i>	Jangli kaua	Covidae/B
135.	Jangle myna	<i>Acridotheres fuscus</i>	Jangli mayna	Sturnidae/B
136.	Owlet	<i>Glaucidium radiatum</i>	Jangli chaughad	Strcidae/B
137.	Purpie moorhen	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	Jal murgi	Rallidae/B
138.	Nukta ducker comb duck	<i>Sarkidiornis melanoros</i>	Nakta	Anatidae/ B
139.	Black headed munia	<i>Lonchura malacca</i>	Nakal nar	Ploceidae/B
140.	Indian roller blue joy	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	Nilkanth	Coracidae/B
141.	Indian pitta	<i>Pitta brachyura</i>	Navrang	Pittiidae/B
142.	Paddy bird pond heron	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	Andha bagla	Ardeidae/B
143.	Grey heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Anjan	Ardeidae/B
144.	Pied myna	<i>Sturnus contra</i>	Ablak myna	Sturnidae/B
145.	Rufus tailed finch lark	<i>Ammomanes phoenicurus</i>	Aagiya	Alaudidae/B
146.	Tawny eagle	<i>Aquila refax</i>	Okab	Accipitridae/ B
147.	Painted snipe	<i>Rostratula benghalensis</i>	Ohadra	Rostratuliridae/B
148.	Blossom headed parakeet	<i>Psittacula cynocephala</i>	Tuiya tota	Psittacidae/B
149.	Cattle egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Gay bagla	Ardeidae/B
150.	Open bull stork	<i>Anostomus oscitans</i>	Godhila	Ciconidae/B
151.	House sparrow	<i>Passer domestica</i>	Goraiya	Ploidae/B
152.	Cottontail	<i>Nettapus coromon delianus</i>	Gurguri pandubbi	Anatidae/B
153.	Black winged stilts	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>	Gajpin	Recurvirostidae/B
154.	White neck stork	<i>Ciconia episcopus</i>	Galgal	Ciconidae/B
155.	White stork	<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>	Galgal	Ciconidae/B
156.	Jangle bush quail	<i>Perdicula asiatica</i>	Lawa	Phasiamidae/B
157.	Red crested pochard	<i>Netta rufina</i>	Losir	Anatidae/B
158.	Red mania	<i>Estrilda amandava</i>	Lal munia	Ploidae/B
159.	Indian Clift swallow	<i>Hirundo fluvicola</i>	Lesra	Hirundidae/B

160.	Wire tailed swallow	<i>Hirundo smithii</i>	Lesra	Hirundidae/B
161.	Common Buzzerd	<i>Buteo buteo</i>	Bazard	Accitridae/B
162.	Cobra/ black	<i>Naja naja</i>	Nag	Squamata/ R
163.	Krait	<i>Bangarus ceeruleus</i>	Karet	Squamata /R
164.	Resell viper	<i>Vipera russelli</i>	Vaipar	Squamata /R
165.	Python	<i>Python molurus</i>	Ajgar	Squamata /R
166.	Cobra	<i>Naja tripudians</i>	Nag	Squamata /R
167.	Chameleon	<i>Chameleon zeyllanicus</i>	Harasap	Squamata /R
168.	Calottes	<i>Melanochelys trijuga</i>	Girgit	Squamata /R
169.	Tortoise	<i>Trijuga trijuga</i>	Kachhua	Squamata /R
170.	Barb	<i>Barbus putitora</i>	Mahur	Siluriformes /F
171.	Flying barb	<i>Esomus denricus</i>	Kudna	Cipriniformes /F
172.	Labeo	<i>Labeo gonius</i>	Khursa	Cipriniformes /F
173.	Spotted snake head	<i>Channa punctatus</i>	Bhagna	Perciformes /F
174.	Stinging cat fish	<i>Hetropneustes fossilis</i>	Sawal	Siluriformes/ /F
175.	Snake headed barb	<i>Ophiocephalus striatus</i>	Bhunda	Siluriformes/ /F
176.	Walking cat fish	<i>Clarius batrachus</i>	Magur	Siluriformes/ /F
177.	Zig zag eel	<i>Mastacembelus armatus</i>	Bam	Mastacembeliformis/F
178.	Barb	<i>Barbus sarana</i>	Kunda	Siluriformes/F
179.	Wallago	<i>Wallago attu</i>	Padhan	Siluriformes/ /F
180.	Bata	<i>Labeo bata</i>	Bhanga	Cipriniformes /F
181.	Day's Mystus	<i>Mystus bleekeri</i>	Singan	Siluriformes/F
182.	Dwarf goonch	<i>Bagarius bagarius</i>	Bend	Siluriformes/F
183.	Labeo	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	Rohi	Cipriniformes /F

Source:– Office of the Forest Conservator, West Forest Division of Chhindwara.

Table-2: List of Taxonomy Group of Animals of West Division of Chhindwara.

S.No.	Taxonomy group of animal	Total number of animals
1.	Pisces	14
2.	Reptiles	8
3.	Birds	125
4.	Mammals	36

Fig. – 1: Animal Diversity of West Forest Division Chhindwara.

Table-3: Endangered species of the area.

S.No.	Name of Animal	Group
1	<i>Panthera tigris,</i>	Mammals
2	<i>Panthera pardus,</i>	‘’
3	<i>Bos gaurus</i>	‘’
4	<i>Tetraceros quadricornis</i>	‘’
5	<i>Canis alpinus</i>	‘’

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

As a result of periodic and extensive study made in around west division of Chhindwara district. Over 182 animal species were identified as belonging to having 182 species belonging to 146 genera and 94 families. Out of the documented animal species 36 were mammals and 125 birds in this area. Table-1 given the list of species, along with there local names, scientific name, English name and class/ family. Out of 182 species, 36 are mammals (20%), 125 are birds (68%), 08 reptiles (4%) and 14 Pisces (8%), (Table-2, Fig-2), given the list of animal diversity of west division. Table-3 given the list of 05 animal species *Panthera tigris*, *Panthera pardus*, *Bos gaurus*, *Tetraceros quadricornis* and *Canis alpinus* are endangered in this area. Local people are using some animals to cure different diseases. Due to mining, deforestation, fire and hunting of animal species are becoming rare in the area.

Biodiversity underpins the form and function of ecosystems, which are of high value due to the life-supporting services they provide that meet human needs, both material and non-material. Biodiversity supports ecosystem services that have economic value for humans in terms of direct or indirect use. They are provisioning services, such as supplying of fuel and fodder, and regulating services, such as carbon sequestration and prevention of soil erosion. Moreover, biodiversity has non-use or existence value. For millions of Indians, biodiversity supports their very livelihoods and ways of life. In the Indian context especially, a range of socio-cultural values are derived from biodiversity that are philosophical, cultural and religious. Biodiversity and ecosystem diversity are reflected in the cultural and religious diversity of India through the varied values attached to biodiversity components and landscapes. India's many traditional knowledge systems and ethnomedicinal practices are based on a close understanding of and dependence on biodiversity. The Tiger *Panthera tigris* is an umbrella species for conservation of the biota of a majority of the eco-regions in Asia. Its role as a top predator is vital in regulating and maintaining ecological processes and systems. India is home to over 50% of the world's wild tigers in spite of having a growing human population of over a billion Wildlife conservation faces several formidable challenges.

A large number of wild animal species occur outside the PA system. Recovery of critically endangered species and their habitats requires priority attention. With this in view, the erstwhile MoEF scheme of 'Assistance for the Development of National Parks and Sanctuaries' was reformulated and renamed as Integrated Development of Wildlife Habitats (DWH) during the 11th plan period (2007-2012). The scheme incorporates additional components/activities for implementing the provisions of the Wildlife (Protection) Act 1972, and National Wildlife Action Plan (2002-2016), the recommendations of the Tiger Task Force, 2005, and the National Forest Commission, 2006, and the necessities felt from time to time for conservation of wild animals and their habitats.

PHOTO GALLERY

Mastocembelus armatus

Clarias batrachus

Wallago attu

Channa striatus

Notopterus notopterus

Cyprinus carpio

Passur domesticus

Sturnia pagodarum

Gallus gallus

Cinnyris asiaticus

Melanophryniscus spp.

Funambulus funambulus

Pteropus gigantius

Bos gaurus

Copsychus saularis

CONCLUSION

Wildlife habitat and species around the world are facing a crisis. It is estimated that global warming may cause the extinction of 15–37% of species by 2050. This is another aspect which needs attention because we could lose about 1.25 million species. Unlike other environmental losses, this one cannot be reversed because nature does not give second chances to biodiversity.

If we take into consideration the conventional reasons why wildlife is disappearing in Asia, India is doing far better than other countries. India has launched an extensive protected area network of research institutions in which legislation, socio-economic factors, and wildlife research are playing a great role. The Central Zoo Authority plays a key role with zoos in programming research activities related to the conservation and propagation of wild animals. Planned research activities include studies on wildlife biology, genetic variability, species-specific nutritional requirements, animal behavior, epidemiological surveys, and disease diagnosis through postmortem examination.

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